

The Sensitivity and Specificity of Different Laboratory Parameters in Septicemia in Paediatric Age Group Patients: An Observational Study Conducted in a Rural Medical College Hospital

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Received: 29-10-2024 / Revised: 28-11-2024 / Accepted: 27-12-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Sepsis, one of the leading causes of severe illness worldwide, is a potentially fatal organ failure brought on by a dysregulated host response to infection. The aim of present study is to evaluate the specificity and sensitivity of C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin (PCT), Band cell count and toxic granules in septicemia in pediatric age group.

Material and Methods: The present observational study, was conducted in a government rural medical college hospital catering mostly to the rural population under its jurisdiction for a period of 6 months among 100 patients selected on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria. Blood samples were collected from all patients and evaluated for CRP, PCT, Band cell count and Toxic granule. Results were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0.

Results: Prevalence of septicaemia was found to be 65%. The mean value of CRP was 6.87 ± 2.1 mg/dL, mean Procalcitonin was 3.67 ± 0.89 ng/ml. the number of patients with band cell count $<10\%$ was 39 (60%) and $\geq 10\%$ was 26 (40%). Maximum patients 23 (35.3%) had +2 toxic granules. CRP with AUC 0.865 had a sensitivity and specificity of 83.9%, 75.6%. PCT with AUC 0.694 had sensitivity and specificity of 80.21%, 73.4%. Band cell count had AUC 0.346 with sensitivity and specificity of 78.39%, 70.31%. Toxic granules had AUC 0.321 with sensitivity and specificity of 75.69% and 69.87%. There were statistically significant positive correlations between sepsis and biomarker like CRP, PCT, Band cell count and toxic granules ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Abnormal CRP combined with PCT, toxic granules and band cell count may be a straight forward and accurate method for quickly identifying neonatal sepsis.

Keywords: Band Cell Count, CRP, PCT, Sensitivity, Specificity, Sepsis, Toxic Granules

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Introduction

Sepsis is a life-threatening organ failure resulting from a dysregulated host response to infection and remains one of the primary causes of critical illness globally. It encompasses physiological, pathological, and biochemical anomalies generated by infection; nevertheless, the host's response to an invading pathogen is equally significant, since it can be exacerbated and dysregulated.[1] The original definition of sepsis, based on at least two criteria of systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS), emphasized an excessive inflammatory response. It is now acknowledged that sepsis pathways entail the activation of pro- and anti-inflammatory responses. [2,3]

Despite extensive research on sepsis in recent years, a consensus on its clinical definition remains elusive. The International Pediatric Sepsis Consensus Conference defined sepsis as systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) occurring in conjunction with or as a consequence of suspected or confirmed infection.[4] The definitions for adult sepsis have been revised, whereas the definition of pediatric sepsis remains unaltered. Nonetheless, research on pediatric sepsis has been conducted, and various novel methodologies have been suggested, such as the pediatric Sequential Organ Failure Assessment score (pSOFA).[5]

Upon suspicion of sepsis, a clinical evaluation must be supplemented with laboratory investigations. Blood culture is the definitive method for detecting sepsis and must be conducted in every suspected case prior to initiating medications. The total leukocyte count, differential cell count, absolute neutrophil count, and band cell percentage relative to total neutrophils (immature to total neutrophil ratio) are additional diagnostics; however, they lack sensitivity when assessed quickly after presentation.[6] Biomarkers can be quantitatively assessed and function as definitive indications of normal biological and pathological processes, or the response to treatment interventions.[7]

The methods currently employed to differentiate between bacterial and viral illnesses generally include white blood cell (WBC) counts, C-reactive protein (CRP), and procalcitonin (PCT) levels. WBC offers diagnostic utility for confirming severe infections, with positive probability ratios ranging from 0.87 to 2.43.[8] CRP demonstrates a sensitivity of 75%, specificity of 67%, and an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.77 in differentiating patients with sepsis from those with non-infectious SIRS.[9] PCT exhibits a sensitivity of 77% and a specificity of 0.79 for diagnosing sepsis in severely unwell patients. The search for biomarkers that can reliably and early assess the probability of bacterial infection, risk stratification, and mortality risk persists, and now, no singular biomarker can accurately predict sepsis.[10]

The need of the hour is a sound system of early and accurate diagnosis of sepsis to optimize antimicrobial treatment and to prevent overtreatment and misuse. The aim of this study is to evaluate the specificity and sensitivity of C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin (PCT), Band cell count and toxic granules in septicemia. A biomarker, which can easily, rapidly, and accurately help diagnosing septicemia will help in better management of septicemia particularly in a poor resource srset up.

Material and Methods

The present observational study was conducted in a government rural medical college hospital catering mostly to the rural population under its jurisdiction. During the study period of 6 months. Ethical clearance was taken from the Internal ethics committee of medical college before commencement of study. Guardian/Parents of paediatric patients were asked to sign an informed consent form after explaining them about the study in vernacular language. This study was conducted

in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and the standard of good clinical practice.

Through convenient sampling method a total of 100 paediatric patients who visited to hospital were selected on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria: Suspected septicemic patients of paediatric age group, admitted to the paediatric ward of this institution and later confirmed by blood culture.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with blood malignancy, immunodeficiency diseases, and those being treated with immunosuppressive medications.

Blood samples were collected from all patients on admission for automated complete blood count, CRP, PCT, Band cell count, Toxic granule, serum creatinine, bilirubin, arterial blood gas analysis and blood culture.

For supportive diagnosis and to identify the suspected source of infection based on clinical suspicion, appropriate blood/ pus/urine/body fluid cultures and imaging studies were done. Clinical diagnosis with culture results were considered as standard for this study.

Data was collected in two steps, firstly patient specific data was collected at bedside using predesigned and pretested questionnaires and laboratory data was collected from central laboratory records.

Data was checked for inconsistencies and errors and was analyzed using descriptive statistics in MS Excel and SPSS softwares. A receiver operator characteristic (ROC) curve was plotted for each of the markers and area under the curve (AUC) was calculated for each parameter to evaluate the validity and accuracy of the tests. The Youden's index was used to determine the best cutoff values for each parameter, and the best sensitivity and specificity was calculated. Diagnostic odds ratio (DOR) was calculated to find the best predictive parameter in the study period. A p value less than 0.05 will be considered as statistically significant. An overall qualitative analysis was considered. Some changes could be employed during the statistical analysis pertaining to the aftermath of the study.

Results

Out of 100 suspected patients 65 had confirmed septicaemia while 35 does not have septicaemia as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Prevalence of septicemia among patients

The mean age of patients was 1.5±1.0 years. Number of female patients were 22 (33.9%) and male patients were 43 (66.1%). The most common origin of infection was respiratory system 25 (38.4%) and common organism found was *Klebsiella pneu-*

moniae 15 (23.07%). Mechanical ventilation was needed in 35 (53.8%). Mean length of stay at hospital was 7.3±2.0 days. Rate of complication was 21 (32.3%) and mortality rate was 14 (21.5%) as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic data and clinical characteristics of patients with septicemia (n=65)

Variable		Values
Mean age (years)		1.5±1.0
Gender	Male	43 (66.1)
	Female	22 (33.9)
Infection origin	Respiratory	25 (38.4)
	Digestive	13 (20)
	Urinary	10 (15.3)
	CNS	9 (13.8)
	Other	8 (12.3)
Pathogens found	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	15 (23.07)
	<i>Neisseria meningitidis</i>	12 (18.4)
	<i>E.coli</i>	12 (18.4)
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	10 (15.3)
	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	9 (13.8)
	Others	7 (10.7)
Mechanical ventilation		35 (53.8)
Mean length of stay at hospital (days)		7.3±2.0
Complications		21 (32.3)
Mortality		14 (21.5)

The mean value of CRP was 6.87±2.1 mg/dL, mean Procalcitonin was 3.67±0.89 ng/ml. the number of patients with band cell count <10% was 39

(60%) and ≥10% was 26 (40%). Maximum patients 23 (35.3%) had +2 toxic granules as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Laboratory findings of patients with sepsis

Laboratory Findings		Values
C-reactive protein (mg/dL)		6.87±2.1
Procalcitonin (ng/ml)		3.67±0.89
Band cell count	<10%	39 (60)
	≥10%	26 (40)
Toxic granules	0	15 (23.0)
	+1	20 (30.7)
	+2	23 (35.3)
	+3	7 (10.7)

Analysis of biomarkers using ROC curve in the patients for sepsis was done and it was found that

CRP with AUC 0.865 had a sensitivity and specificity of 83.9%, 75.6%. PCT with AUC 0.694 had sensitivity and specificity of 80.21%, 73.4%.

Band cell count had AUC 0.346 with sensitivity and specificity of 78.39%, 70.31%. Toxic granules had AUC 0.321 with sensitivity and specificity of 75.69% and 69.87% as shown in table 3. (figure 2)

Table 3: Analysis of biomarkers using ROC curve in the patients for sepsis

Parameter	AUC	P value	Sensitivity	Specificity
CRP	0.865	<0.001	83.9%	75.6%
PCT	0.694	<0.001	80.21%	73.4%
Band cell count	0.346	<0.001	78.39%	70.31%
Toxic granules	0.321	<0.001	75.69%	69.87%

Figure 2: Sensitivity and specificity of CRP, PCT, Band cell count and Toxic granules

There were statistically significant positive correlations between sepsis and biomarker like CRP, PCT,

Band cells count and toxic granules ($p < 0.001$) as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Correlation between sepsis and diagnostic markers in the study group

Biomarker	r	p
CRP	0.659	<0.001
PCT	0.620	<0.001
Band cell count	0.543	<0.001
Toxic granules	0.510	<0.001

Discussion

The majority of haematological and biochemical tests, including the neonatal sepsis screen, have the advantage of being easy to perform even in the side laboratories (typically connected to the wards) without the need for complex equipment, in addition to having results quickly (usually within an hour). A diagnostic marker with a very high sensitivity (infected infants have a positive test) and negative predictive value (a negative test

confidently rules out infection) approaching 100% is desirable given the high mortality and serious morbidity associated with neonatal sepsis. This is because all septic infants should be identified early and treated. [11,12]

In the present observational study, conducted in a government rural medical college hospital catering mostly to the rural population under its jurisdiction we evaluated the specificity and sensitivity of C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin (PCT), Band

cell count and toxic granules in pediatric population suspicious of septicemia.

In our study the prevalence of septicemia was found to be 65%. The patients were 1.5 ± 1.0 years old on average. There were 43 (66.1%) male patients and 22 (33.9%) female patients. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 15 (23.07%) was the most frequently detected pathogen, while respiratory system 25 (38.4%) was the most frequently reported source of infection. In 35 cases (53.8%), mechanical ventilation was required. The average hospital stay lasted 7.3 ± 2.0 days and the complication rate was 21 (32.3%). In a study done by Aygun et al of the 68 sepsis patients, 31 (45.6%) were men and 37 (54.4%) were women. Their median age was 1.1 years, with a range of 1 month to 17.8 years. The respiratory system (n = 30, 44.1%) and digestive system (n = 12, 17.6%) were the most common causes of infection. *Neisseria meningitidis* (7 patients), *Escherichia coli* (7 patients), and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (10 patients) were the most frequently identified microorganisms from the cultures. The patients with sepsis spent an average of 7.0 days (26 hours to 97 days) in the PICU.[13]

The mortality rate in our study was 14 (21.5%). In a study done by Nguyen-Huu CD et al 29.0% perished and 71.0% lived.[14] Of the children who died, 35% passed away within the first 24 hours of being admitted for resuscitation. Our results show a greater death rate when compared to international research. According to Mishra et al, sepsis in PICU settings has a 7.3% fatality rate.[15] A mortality rate of 6% (51/795) was observed by Boeddha et al. [16]

There were statistically significant positive correlations between sepsis and biomarker like CRP, PCT, Band cell count and toxic granules ($p < 0.001$).

Analysis of biomarkers using ROC curve in the patients for sepsis was done and it was found that CRP with AUC 0.865 had a sensitivity and specificity of 83.9%, 75.6%. PCT with AUC 0.694 had sensitivity and specificity of 80.21%, 73.4%. Although CRP has long been used to diagnose sepsis, its specificity has recently been called into question because it also rises in cases of burns, ischaemia, trauma, and other inflammatory conditions. However, elevated CRP concentrations are linked to a higher risk of organ failure and death.[17] Different cut-off values should be used by doctors based on whether they wish to confirm or rule out sepsis [9]. In a study done by Rautiainen et al, sepsis patients had far higher CRP levels than non-sepsis patients; at a cut-off level of 69.9 mg/L, it predicted sepsis with an 82% sensitivity and a 64% specificity.[18] PCT is also commonly used in conjunction with CRP and has been suggested as a more accurate and specific prognostic indicator

than CRP. According to a meta-analysis, the detection of sepsis has a 76% sensitivity and a 69% specificity.[19]

Toxic granules had AUC 0.321 with sensitivity and specificity of 75.69% and 69.87%. In a study done by Hoq AA et al 91.67% of newborns with positive blood cultures had toxic granules in their neutrophils.[20] When diagnosing sepsis, the toxic granules' sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV were 91.66%, 75%, and 91.66%, respectively. In the study by Narasimha A et al, the characteristics were determined to be 78.12%, 94.44%, 92.59%, and 82.92%.[21]

Band cell count had AUC 0.346 with sensitivity and specificity of 78.39%, 70.31%. In a study done by Senzel LB et al [22] abnormal band counts were present in 5 of 70 specimens. Hence, a relatively higher band count is seen in bacterial infections that primarily cause lower respiratory tract disease and are associated with more parenchymal inflammation at the time of ER presentation.

There were various restrictions on our investigation. There was little data extrapolation to bigger populations because this was a single centre study conducted in a rural setting. It is challenging to compare and interpret our findings because some of the makers, such as toxic granules and band cell count, have not been thoroughly explored in paediatric sepsis.

Conclusion

According to the results of this study, abnormal CRP combined with PCT, toxic granules and band cell count may be a straightforward and accurate method for quickly identifying neonatal sepsis in patients of the condition that have not been treated with previous medications. Although out of all the markers, CRP has the highest sensitivity and specificity, but, relying solely on the abnormalities of one sepsis screen marker may lead to the unintentional overtreatment of the vast majority of neonates who are not infected.

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